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Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)

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August 2021

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Mandal, Netai; Das, Amalendu; Mondal, Debajyoti; and Das, Suman, "Analysis of the literature growth and usability of YouTube videos related to Moodle" (2021). *Library Philosophy and Practice (e-journal)*. 6019. <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/libphilprac/6019>

Analysis of the literature growth and usability of YouTube videos related to Moodle

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Abstract

YouTube is one of the largest social media platforms. In 2005 YouTube had started its journey, and today it has more than 2.3 billion users. After pandemic new normal situation people are very much dependable on YouTube. People watch share, comments and likes on videos transferred by the maker. The current investigation aims to look at the attributes of YouTube videos identified with Moodle e-learning software. In this Pandemic condition it is open-source advanced e-learning software utilized in numerous Institutions. In this study we found 560 videos found related to Moodle. Researchers find that out of 560 Moodle videos, 76 % HD and 24% SD videos. Also, show that 504 videos have sound and 56 videos have not sound. In the examination additionally showed that the vast majority of the video are identified with the prologue to Moodle and Moodle installation. The investigation additionally talked about the length of videos and top fifteen (15) views, comments and likes, dislike videos identified with Moodle and also found more videos on Moodle from various channel IDs according to the user's point of view. The investigation saw that the Moodle installation videos uploaded by YouTubers having a more significant influence on people.

Keyword: *Moodle, E-learning Software, content analysis, YouTube Videos, Online class, Online Videos.*

Introduction

Today, YouTube is the most used online video store on the web for intelligent learning. This likewise gives clients a spot to communicate their perspectives about videos in the structure remarks and rating. Moreover, YouTube is an online popular video site that has uploaded many videos on different areas that may describe a product, their services or Tutorial about software. Likewise, YouTube received a massive amount of comments from the viewers. Moodle is a Learning Management software that was also very popular content on YouTube. In this study, the researcher wants to content analysis of Moodle videos which was available on YouTube.

About Moodle

Moodle is a freeware software, and it was written in PHP language. Moodle is one of the famous and most significant learning management software worldwide. Most academic institutions such as schools, colleges, University use Moodle for distance learning, blended learning, learning management, flipped classrooms, course management and resources management. Moodle is also used extensively for websites. Martin Dougiamas initially developed Moodle to assist instructors with making on the web courses, emphasising communication and collective development of content. Moodle first version was released on 20 August 2002. In Web server (Like Apache HTTP Server, MySQL etc) anybody can download and introduce Moodle. It runs without adjustment on Windows, OS X, UNIX, Linux, FreeBSD, NetWare, and other systems supporting PHP.

Related Work:

Content analysis research output of YouTube videos became very popular from the beginning of the second decade of the twenty-first century. Wellbourne, D and Grant, W, (2015) analyzed 390 YouTube videos from 39 YouTube channels and showed that expertise produced subject matter was great in number, user produced content was essentially more extensive. Moreover, regular science contact videos were more popular than non-regular contact videos. This study describes the first steps needed to understand the elements of content by developing science channels and video popularity on YouTube.

Thelwal, M, (2017) introduces and critiques a regular social media analysis system to acquire bits of knowledge on any theme from YouTube. The investigation shows that a set of dance-style videos to detect tainted types of sub-topic in differences gender, and sensitivity. However, the investigation focuses to the conventional limits of online media analysis derived to the nature of their basic investigative in various methods.

Tao, D, Adsul, P., War, R., Jupka, K., Semar, C. and Goggins, K., (2012) conducted research to test whether a search method worked by applying different search items. Provides statistics on the use of tobacco products and videos on YouTube and statistics on community engagement, which examines the significance of YouTube videos. The survey tracked down that a couple of search terms out of a sum of 17 terms were more powerful as far as the importance of recovered videos and additionally YouTube has generated video utilization and community consultation statistics have not significantly affected that has been relevance to the redeem videos.

Deuri, M., Kumar, V. And Verma, M. (2021) have conducted comparative studies to evaluate some of the features of DSpace and Koha software videos available on YouTube. The webmetric analyst

has released a total of 461 and 397 videos uploaded to the YouTube platform from Koha and DSP, respectively. The survey results suggested that while the increase rate of Koha videos is declining, DSpace video has increased steadily. Sensory analysis of 2043 and 862 comments found in Koha and DSpace videos, respectively, of which "positive" comments are the most common, and the most helpful "response" intent with "happy" emotion can be identified in both Koha and DSpace videos.

Chui, L. And f, l. (2021) examines the YouTube videos related to the crash and analyses which features play a role in making a video popular with the audience and determines to the content and remarks of the videos quantitatively. For example, there were more likes and comments every day on videos about the current situation in Fukushima. In addition, the video recorders who directly inspect Fukushima officially found more customers, likes and more views.

Huang, J., Cornfield, R., and Emery, S. (2016) examines the amount of e-cigarette-related videos on YouTube, evaluate content and identify the level of arrangement. Understanding the advancement and conversation of e-cigarettes on YouTube can assist with explaining the stage's effect on purchaser perspectives and behavior and information laws. YouTube is a powerful platform for sharing information for an electronic cigarette. However, YouTube seems to have been used unevenly by electronic cigarette for promotional purposes.

Gooding, L and Gregory, D., (2011) conduct a study of YouTube videos related to music therapy. The authors have analysis the circulation of information about music therapy. Also observe the ethical stander of the music therapy YouTube videos.

Methods:

The information was extricated from YouTube utilising Webometrics Analyst programming by making YouTube API. A Search word "Moodle" insert to Webometrics Analyst programming and 560 videos observed relating to Moodle. A few videos were taken out due to irrelevant and not give data to Moodle. After confirming authentic and relatable Moodle videos, looking for the video's id for inquiry, the comments, Subscriber, like, dislike, video quality per video were extracted using Webometric Analyst.

Data analysis and results:

Top fifteen commented videos:

Year	Title	Channel Title	Comment Count
2020	HOW To HACK MOODLE Quiz Tests Exams and find All Kinds of ANSWERS including SUBJECTIVE Online TRICK!	Sohamn Pramanik	727
2015	How To Import A Quiz From Word Document To Moodle	FacultyWorkshop	494
2014	How to set up a Free Moodle platform and create courses (Cómo configurar una plataforma Moodle Gratis y crear cursos)	ExcellereConsultora	382
2019	How to register in the Moodle app for university students. (لطلبة الجامعات Moodle طريقة التسجيل في تطبيق)	قناة الجود	221
2020	How to Create an LMS Educational Website like UCLA with WordPress & Moodle 2021 - Moodle Tutorial	Darrel Wilson	206
2020	Moodle course for teachers(curso de Moodle para profesores)	Yoney Gallardo	206
2019	E Learning Moodle Pemula Sampai Mahir [Offline Sampai Hosting]	Belajarnesia Channel	164
2018	Moodle for Beginners, An introduction to the free Moodle cloud.	Tefl-Dude	162
2020	How to Hack Moodle Copy and Paste on Moodle Moodle Clipboard Solution	Cyber School	145
2019	How to install Moodle on my computer?(Como instalar o Moodle no meu computador?)	Marcelo Claro	132
2020	MOODLE Where to start?(MOODLE С чего начать?)	Time to Talk with Yevgen	128
2020	How to access the Moodle account(Comment accéder au compte Moodle كيفية الولوج إلى حساب مودل (FLDM))	Fayçal Seffar	125
2020	how to create questionnaires - questions and rate on Moodle(cómo crear cuestionarios - preguntas y calificar en)Moodle	YouTics	121
2020	install Moodle step by step ((easy install - 2021))[instalar Moodle paso a paso ((instalación fácil - 2021))]	Brandom Stalin	112
2020	How to SELL Courses with MOODLE(Cómo VENDER Cursos con MOODLE)	Roxana Falasco	109

Table 1:- Top fifteen commented videos

From the above Table no 1,we found that the 15 most remarked videos identified with MOODLE Software. Moreover, the information uncovers that the title " How To Import A Quiz From Word Document To Moodle" got 727 comments by Sohamn Pramanik got the first position. The

information likewise illuminates that the title identified with fundamental data to establishment and methodology of MOODLE was, for the most part, remarked by viewers.

Video Quality:

Figure 1:- Video Quality

In this study we show (Figure -1) that the various qualities of MOODLE videos. Out of 560 no of videos 94% of videos discovered HD (high definition) videos while only 6% discovered standard definition (SD) videos.

Video license:

For this examination, the analyst had gathered 560 awesome videos collect from the YouTube website, data identified with MOODLE, coming from total 560 videos, 449 videos are licensed under YouTube permit while 111 videos are licensed under Creative Commons (cc). Besides, the information illuminates that most of the videos published on YouTube having YouTube license in contrast with CC (Creative Common license.)

Fig 2:Video Licence

Growth of MOODLE Videos:

Table 2 & Fig 3- Growth of MOODLE Videos

This table shows that the growth of YouTube videos identified with MOODLE from 2007-2021. Out of 560 videos, a more significant part of (212) videos uploaded in the year 2020. Developments of MOODLE videos are not steady, and growth rate of Moodle video was some time up and some time down. However, from 2007-2009 the growth rate of uploaded videos was up and down, but in 2012-2020 the growth rate of YouTube videos was incensing.

Top Ten Like videos:

Year	Title	Channel Title	Like Count	Dislike Count
2020	HOW To HACK MOODLE Quiz Tests Exams and find All Kinds of ANSWERS including SUBJECTIVE Online TRICK!	Sohamn Pramanik	5040	1032
2015	How To Import A Quiz From Word Document To Moodle	FacultyWorkshop	4592	95
2020	CURSO DE MOODLE PARA PROFESORES	Yoney Gallardo	3374	132
2014	Cómo configurar una plataforma Moodle Gratis y crear cursos	ExcellereConsultora	1954	109
2019	Jingo Rest Framework & React Tutorial: Learning Management System (Blackboard / Moodle Clone)	freeCodeCamp.org	1954	36
2017	Introducción a Moodle como profesor	Bureau Veritas Formación	1880	81
2011	O que é Moodle - Moodle Academy	MoodleAcademy	1814	19
2018	Moodle for Beginners, An introduction to the	Tefl-Dude	1685	71

	free Moodle cloud.			
2020	How to Create an LMS Educational Website like UCLA with WordPress & Moodle 2021 - Moodle Tutorial ☐	Darrel Wilson	1633	37
2020	CURSO DE MOODLE PARA ESTUDIANTES	Yoney Gallardo	1536	121

Table 3 -Top Ten Like videos

In the above Table no 2 represents that the best ten like MOODLE videos was found on YouTube retrieve data and also YouTube site. The retrieve data shows that title "HOW To HACK MOODLE Quiz Tests Exams and find All Kinds of ANSWERS including SUBJECTIVE Online TRICK!" by YouTube channel title "Sohamn Pramanik" most like the video by watchers with 5040 likes. In addition, the information advises that the most like videos by watchers were identified with "How to Import a Quiz from Word Document to Moodle", "how to create LSM education website throw MOODLE", and design of MOODLE e-learning website.

Most View MOODLE videos:

Year	Title	Channel Title	View Count
2020	HOW To HACK MOODLE Quiz Tests Exams and find All Kinds of ANSWERS including SUBJECTIVE Online TRICK!	Sohamn Pramanik	494738
2014	Cómo configurar una plataforma Moodle Gratis y crear cursos	Excellere Consultora	474116
2015	How To Import A Quiz From Word Document To Moodle	Faculty Workshop	322562
2020	CURSO DE MOODLE PARA PROFESORES	Yoney Gallardo	232191
2018	Moodle for Beginners, An introduction to the free Moodle cloud.	Tefl-Dude	207360
2017	Introducción a Moodle como profesor	Bureau Veritas Formación	207021
2011	O que é Moodle - Moodle Academy	Moodle Academy	192909
2019	Django Rest Framework & React Tutorial: Learning Management System (Blackboard / Moodle Clone)	freeCodeCamp.org	120015
2020	CURSO DE MOODLE PARA ESTUDIANTES	Yoney Gallardo	117918
2020	How to Create an LMS Educational Website like UCLA with Word Press & Moodle 2021 - Moodle Tutorial ☐	Darrel Wilson	73802

Table 4- Most View MOODLE videos

In the above Table no 3 we show that different types of people watch different types of video related to MOODLE. " HOW To HACK MOODLE Quiz Tests Exams and find All Kinds of ANSWERS including SUBJECTIVE Online TRICK " by channel Sohamn Pramanik with 4,94,738 views count and get highest no views Followed by the title " Cómo configurar una plataforma Moodle Gratis y crear cursos " by Channel Title Excellere Consultora with 4,74,116 views count. Additionally, the title "How To Import A Quiz From Word Document To Moodle" by channel title Faculty Workshop got the third position with 3,22,562 views. In this tends to be said that HOW To HACK MOODLE Quiz Tests and how to configure and How To Import A Quiz From Word Document To Moodle were for the most part seen by watchers.

Dislike Video:

Year	Title	Channel Title	View Count	Like Count	Dislike Count
2020	¿Se pueden ver las respuestas de un examen en Moodle?	SUBITUS S.A. de C.V	281194	1489	2260
2020	HOW To HACK MOODLE Quiz Tests Exams and find All Kinds of ANSWERS including SUBJECTIVE Online TRICK!	Sohamn Pramanik	494738	5040	1032
2017	Que es Moodle	Mario Alcazar	142113	704	367
2020	How to Hack Moodle Copy and Paste on Moodle Moodle Clipboard Solution	Cyber School	86835	630	311
2020	Tutorial Como Abrir y llenar un examen en Moodle	Lennin Javier	85082	395	292
2015	TUTORIAL COMPLETO MOODLE EN ESPAÑOL	TODOS TUS TUTORIALES	330674	987	148
2020	CURSO DE MOODLE PARA PROFESORES	Yoney Gallardo	232191	3374	132
2020	🚧 INSTALAR MOODLE PASO A PASO ((INSTALACIÓN FÁCIL - 2021))	Brandom Stalin	141376	1126	123
2020	CURSO DE MOODLE PARA ESTUDIANTES	Yoney Gallardo	117918	1536	121
2018	What is Moodle?	Moodle	389294	1166	121

Table 5- Dislike Video

Table 5 represents some dislike MOODLE videos. From this table we show that "Se pueden ver las respuestas de un examen en Moodle?" by YouTube channel title "SUBITUS S.A. de C.V" is the most disliked video by watchers with 2260 dislikes. However, in this analysis, we count like better than dislike comments, and this is a good sign that people were satisfied with the MOODLE videos.

Duration of Videos:

Table 6- & Fig-3 Duration of Videos

Duration of the video is a vital part of this study from the above table it will be found that out of 560 videos, bigger piece of this (311) videos term is between 0.5-15.05 Minutes, followed by 85 videos 15.05-30.05 Minutes, 19 videos length range between 30.05-45.05 minutes, seven(7) videos length range between 45.05-60.05 Minutes long and 23 videos over the one (1)-hour. And also it will be found that most videos more restricted than 30 minutes.

Finding:

The investigation shows significant discoveries of DSpace videos. This above study showed that MOODLE videos were significant because of the popularity of MOODLE software and supported by a significant number of communities. The outcome shows that -

1. A total 560 no of videos 94% of this discovered good quality (HD) while only 6% discovered standard definition (SD) videos.
2. "How To Import A Quiz From Word Document To Moodle" got 727 comments by Sohann Pramanik and got the first position.
3. Out of 560 videos, 449 videos had a YouTube permit, while 111 videos had Creative Common (cc) license.
4. Out of 560 videos, a more significant part of (212) videos uploaded in the year 2020. Though, just one video was upload in the year 2008.
5. Most saw video title" HOW To HACK MOODLE Quiz Tests Exams and find All Kinds of ANSWERS including SUBJECTIVE Online TRICK" by channel Sohann Pramanik with 4,94,738 views got the first position.
6. The information reveals that the title "HOW To HACK MOODLE Quiz Tests Exams and find All Kinds of ANSWERS including SUBJECTIVE Online TRICK!" by YouTube channel title "Sohann Pramanik" most like the video by watchers with 5040 likes got highest no. of like video.
7. Most dislike video title was" Se pueden ver las respuestas de un examen en Moodle?" by channel SUBITUS S.A. de C.V with 2260 dislike count.

The investigation saw that the videos are significantly affecting individuals, which the maker of the videos presents.

Conclusion

The useability and growth of literature of Youtube have too considerable increase after Covid 19 New Normal world. Facilities of synchronous communication Youtuber and viewer can communicate regularly. User shares their feedback through comment, like, dislike etc. The researcher tries to investigate video content and additionally examine users feedback. In this way, the researcher concentrates on this research, how the videos are affecting the communities.

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Lambodara Parabhoi Prem Chand 11th Convention PLANNER-2018 Tripura University, Agartala, Tripura, 15-17 November, 2018 © INFLIBNET Centre, Gandhinagar, Gujarat , Content Analysis of YouTube Videos Related to Drupal, Joomla and WordPress